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Early and protective microglial activation in Alzheimer's Disease

A prospective study using [¹⁸F]DPA-714 PET imaging

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Running title:

Early and protective microglial activation in Alzheimer's Disease: A prospective study using [¹⁸F]DPA-714 PET imaging.

Abstract

Background:

While emerging evidence suggests that neuroinflammation plays a crucial role in Alzheimer's disease (AD), the impact of the microglia response in AD remains a matter of debate. We aimed to study microglial activation in early AD and its impact on clinical progression using a second-generation TSPO PET radiotracer together with amyloid imaging using PiB-PET.

Method:

We enrolled 96 subjects, 64 AD patients and 32 controls, from the IMABio3 study, who had both [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 PET imaging. AD patients were classified as prodromal AD (n=38) and dementia-AD (n= 26). TSPO-binding was measured using a simple ratio method using cerebellar grey matter as reference tissue, taking into account regional atrophy. Images were analysed at the regional (volume of interest, VOI) and at the voxel level. TSPO genotyping allowed the classification of all subjects in High, Mixed and Low Affinity Binders (HAB, MAB, LAB). Thirty HAB+MAB AD patients were dichotomized into slow decliners (SD, n=10) or fast decliners (FD, n=20) after two years of follow-up.

Results:

All AD patients had an amyloid positive PiB-PET. Among controls, 8 had positive amyloid scans (n=6 HAB+MAB), defined as amyloidosis-controls, and were analysed separately. By both VOIs and voxel-wise comparison, TSPO-binding was higher in HAB, MAB and HAB+MAB AD groups compared to controls, especially at the prodromal stage, involving the temporo-parietal cortex. TSPO-binding was positively correlated with MMSE scores and grey matter volume, as well as with PiB binding. Amyloidosis-controls displayed higher TSPO-binding than controls, especially in the frontal cortex. We found higher TSPO-binding in SD than FD, with no difference in PiB binding.

Conclusion:

Microglial activation appears at the prodromal and possibly at the preclinical stage of AD, and seems to play a protective role in the clinical progression of the disease. The extent of microglial activation appears to differ between patients, and could explain the overlap in TSPO binding values between AD patients and amyloidosis-controls.

Keywords: Alzheimer's Disease; Neurodegeneration; Inflammation; Microglia; Dementia; biomarkers; Neuroprotection.

Abbreviations:

PET: positron-emission tomography; TSPO: 18-kDa translocator protein; PiB: Pittsburgh compound B; MMSE: mini mental state examination; CSF: cerebrospinal fluid; FCSRT: Free and Cued Selective Reminding Test; ROCF: Osterrieth complex figure; TMT: Trail Making Test; CDR: clinical dementia rating score; p-AD: prodromal AD group (CDR score of 0.5); d-AD: dementia AD group (CDR score ≥ 1); HAB: high affinity binders; MAB: mixed affinity binders; LAB: low affinity binders; MRI: magnetic resonance imaging; APOE: Apolipoproteine E; VBM: voxel-based morphometry; VOI: volume of interest; SUVR: standard uptake value ratio; GCI: global cortical index; SD: slow decliners (unchanged CDR score after a two years follow-up); FD: fast decliners (increasing CDR score of 0.5 or more)

Introduction

Emerging evidence suggests that neuroinflammation plays a crucial role in the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease (AD) (Heneka *et al.*, 2015). Microglia, the resident phagocytes of the brain, and astroglia are key players in the inflammatory response. Microglia are ubiquitously distributed in the brain and are activated by neuronal cell death or protein aggregation. In AD, the two principal misfolding and aggregating proteins are β -amyloid ($A\beta$) and tau. A marked accumulation and activation of microglia around $A\beta$ plaques has been described in the post-mortem brains of patients with AD and in animal models (Prokop *et al.*, 2013). In humans, the recent discovery of risk variants of gene encoding innate immune system molecules emphasizes the impact of neuroinflammation in AD pathogenesis (Griciuc *et al.*, 2013; Guerreiro *et al.*, 2013). However the question as to whether the microglial activation plays a beneficial or detrimental role is as yet unresolved.

Many reports suggest that microglia are attracted to $A\beta$ deposits, which they internalize and degrade, aiding clearance of $A\beta$ from the brain. However, during the course of the disease, microglia may lose this beneficial effect as they acquire a "toxic" phenotype due to chronic activation and continued production of pro-inflammatory mediators (Michaud and Rivest, 2015; Prokop *et al.*, 2013). Several studies in transgenic mouse models have revealed diverging roles for neuroinflammation in the build up of amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles (Heneka *et al.*, 2015) but the spectrum of glial cell actions and immune related changes in AD is still a matter of controversy and investigation.

In humans, neuroinflammation has been investigated using 18-kDa translocator protein (TSPO) radiotracers by PET, considered as a marker of microglial activation. The first studies

using [¹¹C]PK11195 showed somewhat contradictory results (Cagnin *et al.*, 2001; Edison *et al.*, 2008; Fan *et al.*, 2015; Okello *et al.*, 2009; Schuitemaker *et al.*, 2013; Versijpt *et al.*, 2003; Wiley *et al.*, 2009). There was a tendency toward increased TSPO binding in AD dementia, albeit with a large overlap with controls and no clear conclusion about binding in early AD. These results can perhaps be explained by the radiotracer itself, which suffered from many limitations, due to its highly lipophilic nature, low bioavailability, high non-specific binding and its limited capacity to detect small changes in TSPO expression (Banati *et al.*, 2000; Belloli *et al.*, 2004; Lockhart *et al.*, 2003).

Recent studies using second generation of TSPO radiotracers suggest late but not early development of neuroinflammation, but again results are somewhat heterogeneous (Golla *et al.*, 2015; Kreisl *et al.*, 2013; Lyoo *et al.*, 2015; Varrone *et al.*, 2015; Yasuno *et al.*, 2008, 2012). In addition these studies are limited by small sample sizes and methodological issues relating to the quantification of TSPO binding, that may lead to misinterpretation.

[¹⁸F]DPA-714 belongs to this new generation of TSPO radiotracers, which have a greater affinity and better signal-to-noise ratio than the [¹¹C]PK11195 (Chauveau *et al.*, 2009).

For the first time, aiming to investigate the role of neuroinflammation in early AD, we analysed microglial activation using [¹⁸F]DPA-714 together with amyloid imaging (PiB-PET) in a large cohort of AD patients, at both prodromal and dementia stages, with a 2 year clinical follow-up, taking into account the polymorphism of the TSPO gene responsible for different affinity profiles.

Methods

Study design and participants

All participants were enrolled in the prospective longitudinal IMABio3 study (PHRC-0054-N 2010), which aimed to assess the neuroinflammation in AD. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Salpêtrière Hospital. All subjects provided written informed consent prior to participating.

AD patients were included according to the following criteria: (1) progressive episodic memory impairment, characterized by a low free recall not normalized with semantic cueing (Dubois *et al.*, 2010; Sarazin *et al.*, 2007) (2) absence of extrapyramidal signs; (3) CSF AD profile, when available, defined as score below 0.8, calculated with the formula $A\beta_{42}/(240+[1.18 \times T\text{-tau}])$ (de Souza *et al.*, 2011).

Controls were recruited according to the following criteria: (1) MMSE score $\geq 27/30$ and

normal neuropsychological assessment; (2) CDR=0; (3) no history of neurological or psychiatric disorders; and (4) no memory complaint or cognitive deficit.

We did not include subjects with (1) severe cortical or subcortical vascular lesions, (2) history of autoimmune and inflammatory diseases or chronic migraines, (3) history of psychiatric disorders or drugs abuse.

Among the 114 subjects screened, 103 fulfilled all the inclusion criteria. PET scans could not be achieved for technical problems for 7 subjects. Finally 96 subjects were included in the study: 64 AD patients (age=68±10.3 years) and 32 controls (age=69.7±9 years). CSF biomarkers measures were available for 56/64 AD patients.

AD patients were classified in 2 groups according to their CDR score: 38 patients displayed a CDR score of 0.5, constituting the prodromal AD group (p-AD) and 26 patients displayed a CDR score ≥ 1 constituting the Alzheimer's disease-dementia group (d-AD).

The autonomy of the patients at the prodromal stage was also documented by a normal score or only one item impaired at the first level in the four Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL, ability to use the telephone, independence for transportation, self-administration of medication, ability to handle finances)(Sarazin *et al.*, 2007).

All participants underwent the same procedure including a complete clinical and neuropsychological assessment, brain 3T MRI, [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 PET imaging.

So far, 30 AD patients were followed up annually for two years (n=18 from the p-AD group and n=12 from the d-AD group).

Clinical, functional and cognitive assessment

The neurological and neuropsychological examination included the MMSE, the CDR scale, the MADRS depression scale and tests for assessing verbal and visual episodic memory, executive function, gesture praxis, visuo-constructive function and language.

Apolipoproteine E4 and TSPO genotype

Blood samples were drawn to characterize APOE and TSPO genotypes. On the basis of the rs6971 polymorphism within the TSPO gene, we classified all subjects in High Affinity Binders (HAB), Mixed Affinity Binders (MAB) or Low Affinity Binders (LAB) groups.

MRI acquisition

For each subject a 3D-T1-weighted structural MRI acquisitions was obtained on a 3T MRI scanner (Siemens Trio, 32 channel system, with a 12 channel head coil for signal reception), to aid identification of volumes of interest (VOIs) for subsequent PET image analysis. This sequence provided a high grey/white matter contrast-to-noise ratio and enabled excellent segmentation and accurate co-registration with the PET images.

[¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 Positron emission tomography imaging procedure

Data acquisition

MRI and PET scans were performed within 4 months of each other. [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 PET scans were performed on the same day. Both PET scans were performed on a High Resolution Research Tomograph (HRRT; CTI/Siemens Molecular Imaging, TN, USA)(de Jong *et al.*, 2007). A 6-min brain transmission scan was performed before injection of each radioligand using a ¹³⁷Cs point source to correct the emission scan for tissue attenuation.

[¹¹C]PiB-PET (mean 362±53 MBq) and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 PET (mean 200±15 MBq) were injected intravenously, and PET dynamic acquisitions in list mode lasted up to 90 min. All corrections (attenuation, normalization, random and scatter coincidences) were incorporated in an iterative OSEM reconstruction. The partial volume effect was corrected by directly incorporating resolution modelling (i.e. Point Spread Function modelling) inside the iterative algorithm (Sureau *et al.*, 2008) so that no further post-correction was needed. 10 iterations using 16 subsets were used. Dynamic data were binned into 27 time frames (6×1 min, 7×2 min, 14×5 min). Reconstructed dynamic data were realigned for motion correction according to the process of frame-to-reference image registration in Pmod (version 3.5; PMOD Technologies Ltd.).

Parametric images were created using Brainvisa software (<http://brainvisa.info>). Standard uptake value (SUV) parametric images were obtained by: (a) Averaging late images (intervals of 40-60 minutes for [¹¹C]PiB images and of 60-90 minutes for [¹⁸F]DPA-714 images) (Lavisse *et al.*, 2015; Lopresti *et al.*, 2005) and (b) adjusting for body weight and injected radioligand dose. SUVr parametric images were constructed by dividing each voxel by the corresponding value obtained in the cerebellum grey matter. The cerebellar grey matter used as a pseudo reference region in both PET analysis (de Souza *et al.*, 2011).

Methodological consideration for the DPA-714 analysis

SUVr have the advantage to improve subject tolerability by not requiring arterial catheterization, and is thought to be less variable than the absolute quantitation for TSPO

imaging, potentially due to problems in identifying the correct input function (Guo Q, 2015; Lyoo *et al.*, 2015).

The choice of the time window between 60-90 min to measure DPA-714 uptake is justified by a recent study showing that [¹⁸F]DPA-714 VT was remarkably stable between 60 and 90 min and that the equilibrium between the compartments (of a 2TCM) was reached at 60 min (Lavissee *et al.*, 2015). In our population, the kinetic analysis demonstrated the validity of this time window (60-90 min), during which the ratios between VOIs and cerebellar grey matter were constant (see supplementary data 1).

Because TSPO is present in all structures in the brain, no true reference region devoid of TSPO can be identified. The acceptable alternative is to use a pseudo reference region, relatively spared of AD pathology and for which the radiotracer uptake is independent of the pathological status. The choice of the cerebellar grey matter as pseudo-reference region was based on the following considerations:

- a) Neuropathological data: Cerebellum is devoid of any tau pathology in AD even at the latest stages (Braak stage VI), and deposition of A β peptides is observed only in the advanced amyloid phases (Thal phase V). The cerebellar cortex did not demonstrate microgliosis or astrocytosis (Wood, 2003).
- b) Recent published PET studies: the use of cerebellar grey matter as pseudo reference region has already been validated using another second generation TSPO ligand (Lyoo *et al.*, 2015). In addition, using [¹⁸F]DPA-714, the cerebellar grey matter displayed the lowest VT among all VOIs in controls (Lavissee *et al.*, 2015).
- c) In our population, [¹⁸F]DPA-714 uptake in cerebellar grey matter was, first, lowest among all VOIs in both control and AD groups; second, not different between control and AD subjects according to TSPO binding (see supplementary data 2); third, not different between p-AD and d-AD accordingly to TSPO binding, fourth, not correlated with MMSE, cortical volume and age.

To avoid overspill from sagittal sinus due to TSPO expression in endothelia cells, the cerebellar grey matter, delineated on individual 3DT1MRI was eroded from 4 mm using spherical structuring elements of 4 mm radius, corresponding to more than 1.5 times the spatial resolution of the tomograph (HRRT).

Volume of interest analysis (VOI)

The same method of anatomical segmentation was used for both [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 PET images. An automated segmentation of grey matter was performed to each individual 3D

T1-weighted MRI scans using the VBM8 package (<http://dbm.neuro.uni-jena.de/vbm/>) implemented in SPM8 (Institute of Neurology, London, UK; <http://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm/>). The segmented MRI scans were coregistered with both [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 parametric images of the subject using a standard mutual information algorithm. The automated anatomical labelling (AAL) atlas was deformed to each individual MRI (using the deformation field extracted from VBM8). Each VOI was intersected with the T1 MRI grey matter mask to perform a pseudo atrophy correction. Then this new labelling volume was registered to the individual PET space of [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 parametric images using their respective transformation extracted from the PET-MRI coregistration. Similarly, cerebellar grey matter was identified for each subject and after eroded (4 mm), the region was used as pseudo-reference region.

Application of the AAL atlas to the PET data allowed the calculation of [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 uptake in 76 anatomical regions. The VOI were defined separately for the left and right hemispheres and were then pooled into greater anatomical VOIs, as previously described (de Souza *et al.*, 2011). Briefly, we defined ten VOIs: (1) the frontal, (2) anterior cingulate, (3) medium cingulate, (4) posterior cingulate, (5) precuneus, (6) parietal, (7) temporal, (8) hippocampus, (9) and occipital cortex. A mean [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 SUVr was obtained for each region. As a measure of global cortical burden, we calculated a [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 Global Cortical Index (GCI), representing the subject's mean SUVr of the neocortical regions cited above. Using this methodology, the cut-off of PiB-GCI was set as at 1.45.

Voxel wise analysis

We used SPM8, implemented on a MATLAB platform (Mathworks.inc). Spatially normalized images were smoothed with an 8mm full-width at half-maximum Gaussian filter. Groups were compared using unpaired two-sample t-test, with TSPO genotype as a covariate. For comparison of HAB+MAB AD patients and controls, results were thresholded at the strict $p < 0.05$, Family wise error (FWE) corrected. For controls and amyloidosis-controls comparison, a threshold of $p < 0.01$ was used. For all analysis, a minimum-activated voxel threshold of 20 voxels was applied.

Statistical analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS20 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois) and MedCalc (<http://www.medcalc.org>) software, and figures 3 and 5 were produced using R, a software

environment for statistical computing and graphics (R Core Team, 2014; <http://www.R-project.org/>). Normality of distribution was tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Differences between groups were assessed using Chi2-test, ANOVA, Kruskal-Wallis tests where appropriate. ANOVA, adjusted for TSPO genotype was used to compare DPA binding between AD groups and controls and between amyloidosis-controls and controls (with TSPO genotype as a covariate). To compare DPA uptake between Fast and Slow decliners, we used ANOVA test with confounding factors (age, TSPO genotype and initial MMSE score) as covariates. A Bonferroni correction was used for multiple comparisons. Correlations were performed by using linear partial correlation analysis, taking into account covariates.

Results

Subject characteristics (Table 1, supplementary data 3)

All groups were matched for age. The prevalence of ApoE ϵ 4 carriers was higher among AD patients. In the whole population, the proportion of LAB was lower than MAB and HAB. The proportion of LAB, MAB and HAB was similar in the p-AD, d-AD and control groups.

[¹¹C]PiB-PET analysis

All AD patients had a positive amyloid PET (PiB-GCI>1.45). We found no difference of the mean PiB-GCI and the PiB uptake values in any VOI between the p-AD and d-AD groups.

Among controls, 8 subjects had a positive PiB-PET imaging (PiB-GCI>1.45), constituting the amyloidosis-control group. The other 24 control subjects had no significant PiB retention (PiB-GCI <1.45).

[¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding: Volume of interest analysis (Table 2)

To avoid interpretation bias due to the polymorphism of the TSPO gene, we compared AD and controls accordingly to their binding affinity.

LAB subjects: The DPA-GCI and regional cortical binding (SUVr) did not differ significantly between AD patients (n=6) and controls (n=4) (GCI of 1.23 ± 0.10 and 1.22 ± 0.25 respectively, $p=0.2$, data not shown).

HAB subjects: The AD group showed higher DPA-GCI when compared to controls ($p=0.02$), even at the prodromal stage. Significant higher DPA-714 binding was observed in the medium and posterior cingulate, precuneus, parietal and temporal cortex, especially at the

prodromal stage. The DPA-714 binding was higher at the prodromal stage but without significant difference between p-AD and d-AD groups.

MAB subjects: The AD group showed higher DPA-GCI than controls ($p=0.02$), even at the prodromal stage. The highest DPA-714 uptakes were observed in the same VOIs than those observed in the HAB patients.

HAB+MAB subjects: The same results were found when we pooled all HAB and MAB subjects, taking account the TSPO affinity as a covariate in the analysis.

[¹⁸F] DPA-714 binding: Voxel wise comparison (Figure 1)

Compared to controls, HAB+MAB AD patients showed significant symmetrical [¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding, throughout the temporal and parietal regions (significance threshold set at $p<0.05$, FWE corrected). At the prodromal stage, the results remained significant in the same cortical areas. No difference was found between the p-AD and d-AD groups. An involvement of the frontal cortex was observed in the p-AD but not in the d-AD patients.

Correlations between [¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding and age or APOE

No correlation was found between the age and the DPA-GCI binding in the whole population ($r=0.03$, $p=0.4$ corrected for the CDR and TSPO genotype). Similarly, no correlation was found among controls or among MAB+HAB AD patients.

No difference of DPA-714 binding was observed between groups according to the presence or the absence of at least one ApoE $\epsilon 4$ allele.

Correlations between [¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding and markers of severity: MMSE and cortical atrophy (Figure 2)

In the HAB+MAB group, partial linear correlations showed a significant positive correlation between the DPA-GCI and MMSE scores, even after correction with age and TSPO genotype as covariates ($r=0.31$, $p=0.016$).

We found a positive correlation between the DPA-GCI and the grey matter volume ($r=0.35$, $p=0.004$). The correlations were corrected for age, TSPO genotype and CDR status as covariates. The correlation remained significant, and even stronger, when we restricted the analysis in the p-AD group alone ($r=0.47$, $p=0.006$, with age and TSPO genotype as covariates).

Comparison of [¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding between amyloidosis-controls and PiB negative controls (Figure 3)

The DPA-GCI was significantly higher in the HAB+MAB amyloidosis controls (n=6, defined by a positive amyloid imaging) than in the HAB+MAB controls (n=20, defined by a negative amyloid imaging) (1.39 ± 0.29 and 1.21 ± 0.10 respectively, $p=0.04$ with TSPO genotype as a covariate), with an overlap between both groups. Analysis by VOIs showed a significant higher mean uptake value of the DPA-714 in the cingulum and the precuneus. The voxel wise comparison confirms the data, showing an extension of the neuroinflammation in the frontal cortex ($p<0.01$). The comparison did not resist to strict t-threshold.

Correlations between [¹¹C]PiB and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding (Figure 4)

In HAB+MAB AD patients, the PiB-GCI and DPA-GCI were positively correlated ($r=0.255$, $p=0.031$). When we analysed the correlations in each VOIs that we identified above as having increased neuroinflammation, we found a positive correlation between the PiB and DPA-714 fixation in all of them, except the occipital cortex, in which p values tended to reach the significance threshold. The correlations were adjusted to age, TSPO genotype, CDR score and ApoE $\epsilon 4$ status.

[¹⁸F]DPA-714 cortical binding and disease progression (Figure 5, supplementary data 4)

Forty-nine subjects were followed up during two years, with a standardized protocol including a CDR. Sixteen controls and 2 amyloidosis-controls remained stable. HAB+MAB AD patients (n=30) were dichotomized into slow decliners (SD) or fast decliners (FD) groups on the basis of the progression of the CDR score at the last visit. Ten AD patients remained stable, showing unchanged CDR score (n=5 p-AD and n=5 d-AD at baseline), whereas 20 AD patients declined, with increasing of 0.5 or more of the CDR score (n=13 p-AD and n=7 d-AD at baseline). All patients were treated with cholinesterase inhibitors. We compared the GCI of the DPA binding at baseline between the SD and FD. After adjusting for confounding factors (age, TSPO genotype and initial MMSE score), we found a significant higher GCI-DPA-714 SUV_r in the SD than in the FD group (1.51 ± 0.17 and 1.29 ± 0.1 respectively, $p = 0.001$).

By contrast, no difference was observed for the PiB-GCI measured at baseline between both SD and FD groups, with age as a covariate (2.82 ± 0.19 and 2.63 ± 0.13 respectively, $p=0.11$).

To ensure that the cortical atrophy did not affect the results, we further conducted the same analysis after excluding 2 patients with CDR=2 at baseline. The TSPO binding was higher ($p=0.001$) in the SD group ($n=10$) than in the FD group ($n=18$), without difference in the MMSE and cortical volume at baseline (MMSE= 22.7 ± 3.7 and 20.1 ± 4.3 , respectively; Cortical Volume= 677.4 ± 57 and 625.2 ± 69). Because SD patients were younger than FD (74 ± 11.4 years vs 62.7 ± 8.4 years, $p=0.01$), we verified that (a) the DPA-714 binding was not different in the early and late onset of AD in the whole AD group and in AD patients who were followed during 2 years, and (b) the absence of correlation between age and DPA-714 binding.

Discussion

In this study, we used [^{18}F]DPA-714, a marker of microglial activation, and PiB, a marker of fibrillar amyloid deposition, by PET to investigate *in vivo* the role of neuroinflammation in AD. All AD patients met the new criteria of AD (Dubois *et al.*, 2010), including pathophysiological biomarkers with positive CSF biomarkers and amyloid PET imaging, limiting considerably the risk of including non-AD patients. Moreover, the control group was defined by negative PiB-PET, excluding preclinical AD, whereas amyloidosis-controls defined by positive PiB-PET, suggestive of preclinical AD, were analysed separately. TSPO binding was analysed according to individual TSPO genotype, which influences the radiotracer binding affinity (Owen *et al.*, 2011).

Using both a VOI based method and direct SPM comparison, we found an increase of TSPO binding in AD compared to controls, especially at the prodromal stage, involving preferentially the temporo-parietal cortex. Moreover, higher inflammation as measured by TSPO binding was associated with higher MMSE score and grey matter volume, which are both inversely correlated with AD severity. These correlations remained significant within the p-AD group after correction for age and TSPO genotype, excluding the risk of false positive results caused by the most severe AD patients. Taken together, these data suggest early rather than late microglial activation in AD.

Studies using [^{11}C]PK11195 report microglial activation in MCI patients with amyloid deposition (Edison *et al.*, 2008; Okello *et al.*, 2009), but this observation has not been confirmed with the new second generation TSPO-tracers (Kreisl *et al.*, 2013): increased *in vivo* binding of TSPO was observed in dementia-AD patients using [^{18}F]FEMPA (Varrone *et al.*, 2015); microglial activation was observed in AD, but not at all or only sparsely in MCI-stage of AD using [^{11}C]PBR28 (Kreisl *et al.*, 2013; Lyoo *et al.*, 2015); whilst the only

published study using [¹⁸F]DPA-714 did not account for the effect of TSPO genotype, severely compromising interpretation of the results (Golla *et al.*, 2015). Finally, it should be noted that all these studies included very few p-AD patients (from 4 to 11).

Our results are seemingly at odds with those of Kreisl *et al.*, (Kreisl *et al.*, 2013) who reported neuroinflammation later in the disease progress, in association with increasing severity. In addition, we did not find any correlation between age and TSPO binding. This discrepancy may be explained by the difference in the method for measuring the density of TSPO. Kreisl *et al.* used a metabolite-corrected plasma input model (classical 2-tissue-compartment model) to quantify [¹¹C]PBR-28 binding, while we used a simple ratio method (SUVr) with the cerebellar grey matter as reference tissue to measure the cortical [¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding.

As previously discussed, the pseudo-reference region method has a much lower coefficient of variation than absolute quantification (Lyoo *et al.*, 2015) and, in addition for [¹¹C]PBR28 specifically, variability in blood and tissue has been reported to lead to the high variability in VT (Guo Q, 2015) as employed by Kreisl *et al.*

Of note, our cohort was larger than those previously reported, enabling us to analyse HAB and MAB groups separately, thus reinforcing our results.

We found a positive correlation between PiB and TSPO binding. Previous publications combining imaging neuroinflammation and amyloid reported conflicting results, and should be interpreted with caution due to the limited sample sizes (Cagnin *et al.*, 2001; Edison *et al.*, 2008; Fan *et al.*, 2015; Kreisl *et al.*, 2013; Okello *et al.*, 2009; Wiley *et al.*, 2009). Our correlation, which remained significant after correction for age, severity stage of the disease, ApoE4 and TSPO genotypes, suggests a relationship between fibrillar A β deposition and neuroinflammation.

Whilst the presence of reactive microglia around A β -plaques has been confirmed in both humans and animal models (Prokop *et al.*, 2013), the mechanisms by which amyloid deposits provoke an inflammatory response are not fully understood. One way to address this question is to study the topography of neuroinflammation. Interestingly, the cortical regions in which the TSPO binding was highest were also affected by amyloid deposition, apart from the frontal cortex. Involvement of the frontal cortex was only observed in p-AD patients using both VOIs and SPM methods.

Importantly, when we analysed the amyloidosis-controls, we found not only an increase on TSPO binding compared with controls, but also a more substantial involvement of the frontal cortex rather than the posterior region. This suggests that microglial activation should appear

at the preclinical stage of AD and then follows a dynamic way during the course of the disease.

Longitudinal data showed that high microglial activation observed at baseline was associated with clinical stable progression after two years of follow up, while low microglial activation was associated with rapid decline. FD were younger than SD, as previously reported (Koedam *et al.*, 2010; van der Vlies *et al.*, 2009), however, our results were corrected for age, MMSE at baseline and TSPO genotype, and were not explained by different treatment. Conversely, no difference was observed in PiB binding. These results are in agreement with a recent paper by Ramanan *et al.*, (Ramanan *et al.*, 2015) showing that lower microglial activation, assessed by [¹¹C] PBR28, is associated with rapid cognitive decline in AD.

One important limitation of our results is the methodology used to quantify the DPA-714 binding in the absence of arterial blood sample. No prior study has yet established that DPA-714 can distinguish AD patients and controls using traditional kinetic modeling methods. Given the lack of arterial plasma sampling, we are not able to provide evidence that 1) DPA-714 VT was greater in AD than controls when measured with arterial input function, and 2) that DPA-714 VT did not differ in cerebellum between AD patients and controls. In consequence, we cannot exclude that the SUV_r method may confound the results. In addition, the presence of microglial activation in the cerebellum cannot be formally excluded in AD, even in the absence of amyloid and tau pathology. Even if our data are in agreement with very recent publications (Chakrabarty *et al.*, 2015; Guillot-Sestier *et al.*, 2015; Michaud and Rivest, 2015; Ramanan *et al.*, 2015), further studies with arterial blood function will be necessary to confirm these clinical results.

Taken together, these data suggest that neuroinflammation appears at the prodromal and even possibly preclinical stage of AD, and plays a protective role in the clinical progression of the disease. The extent of microglial activation was heterogeneous among patients, as indicated by the overlap in TSPO binding values between AD patients and amyloidosis-controls. Such heterogeneity may translate into significantly different rates of disease progression. Note that the strict criteria of inclusion, excluding any history of inflammatory and autoimmune diseases, limit the risk that individual microglial activation was due to other factors than AD. Microglial activation is often considered neurotoxic, generating a proinflammatory response sustained over time that can cause neuronal death (Aguzzi *et al.*, 2013). However, microglial stimulation in mice with AD-like pathology has been shown to decrease A β burden (Herber *et al.*, 2004, 2007). Recent studies in mouse models of amyloid pathology suggested that in healthy individuals or in early phases of AD, activated microglia are efficient at migrating

towards A β deposits and clearing them by phagocytosis. As the disease progresses, microglia become progressively dysfunctional, displaying altered activation, migration and functional differentiation (Chakrabarty *et al.*, 2015; Guillot-Sestier *et al.*, 2015; Michaud and Rivest, 2015).

Despite some methodological limitations discussed above, our results provide, for the first time in humans, corroborative evidence in line with this model. Neuroinflammation observed in prodromal AD is likely driven primarily by brain-resident immune cells, especially microglia, in a non-uniform manner among AD patients. Such inter-individual variability in early innate neuroinflammatory response may influence the clinical course of disease progression. Increased early microglia activation may be protective, and a failure to appropriately adapt to chronic amyloid deposition could be an underlying mechanism in neurodegeneration. Such a protective role of early microglial response in AD pathogenesis fosters the clinical interest of microglia-targeted therapeutic approaches (Shechter and Schwartz, 2013). Finally, [^{18}F]DPA-714 PET imaging may prove a valuable innovative tool for accurately assessing neuroinflammation in early and preclinical AD.

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Author's contribution

Conception and design of the study: MB, MS. Acquisition and analysis of data: LH, JL, GD, CL, ML, RAC, LCdS, HC, LD, MB, BD, PG, OC, MCP, MB, MS. Statistical analysis: LH, MS. Figures: LH, RAC. Drafting of the manuscript: LH, JL, GD, MB, MS. Critical revision of the manuscript: all authors. Study supervision and coordination: MB, MS.

Conflict of interest statement:

LH, JL, MB, CL, ML, LCdS, HC, LD, BD, PG, OC, MCP, MB and MS have nothing to disclose in relation with the work under consideration for publication.

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BD has collaborated with Eli Lilly and Affiris, and has received grants for his institution from Roche and Pfizer.

During the two last years, MS has collaborated with Allianz and with the pharmaceutical company Novartis (lecture/speaking).

Ethics committee approval:

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The study was approved by the Ethics Committee Ile de France VI (Pitié-Salpêtrière Hospital). All subjects provided written, informed consent before participating.

This research has been registered on the website <http://clinicaltrials.gov/> under number NCT01775696.

References

Aguzzi A, Barres BA, Bennett ML. Microglia: scapegoat, saboteur, or something else? *Science* 2013; 339: 156–161.

Banati RB, Newcombe J, Gunn RN, Cagnin A, Turkheimer F, Heppner F, et al. The peripheral benzodiazepine binding site in the brain in multiple sclerosis: quantitative in vivo imaging of microglia as a measure of disease activity. *Brain J. Neurol.* 2000; 123 (Pt 11): 2321–2337.

Belloli S, Moresco RM, Matarrese M, Biella G, Sanvito F, Simonelli P, et al. Evaluation of three quinoline-carboxamide derivatives as potential radioligands for the in vivo pet imaging of neurodegeneration. *Neurochem. Int.* 2004; 44: 433–440.

Cagnin A, Brooks DJ, Kennedy AM, Gunn RN, Myers R, Turkheimer FE, et al. In-vivo measurement of activated microglia in dementia. *Lancet Lond. Engl.* 2001; 358: 461–467.

Chakrabarty P, Li A, Ceballos-Diaz C, Eddy JA, Funk CC, Moore B, et al. IL-10 alters immunoproteostasis in APP mice, increasing plaque burden and worsening cognitive behavior. *Neuron* 2015; 85: 519–533.

Chauveau F, Van Camp N, Dollé F, Kuhnast B, Hinnen F, Damont A, et al. Comparative evaluation of the translocator protein radioligands 11C-DPA-713, 18F-DPA-714, and 11C-PK11195 in a rat model of acute neuroinflammation. *J. Nucl. Med. Off. Publ. Soc. Nucl. Med.* 2009; 50: 468–476.

Dubois B, Feldman HH, Jacova C, Cummings JL, Dekosky ST, Barberger-Gateau P, et al. Revising the definition of Alzheimer's disease: a new lexicon. *Lancet Neurol.* 2010; 9: 1118–1127.

Edison P, Archer HA, Gerhard A, Hinz R, Pavese N, Turkheimer FE, et al. Microglia, amyloid, and cognition in Alzheimer's disease: An [11C](R)PK11195-PET and [11C]PIB-PET study. *Neurobiol. Dis.* 2008; 32: 412–419.

Fan Z, Aman Y, Ahmed I, Chetelat G, Landeau B, Ray Chaudhuri K, et al. Influence of microglial activation on neuronal function in Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease dementia. *Alzheimers Dement. J. Alzheimers Assoc.* 2015; 11: 608–621.e7.

Golla SSV, Boellaard R, Oikonen V, Hoffmann A, van Berckel BNM, Windhorst AD, et al. Quantification of [18F]DPA-714 binding in the human brain: initial studies in healthy controls and Alzheimer's disease patients. *J. Cereb. Blood Flow Metab. Off. J. Int. Soc. Cereb. Blood Flow Metab.* 2015; 35: 766–772.

Griciuc A, Serrano-Pozo A, Parrado AR, Lesinski AN, Asselin CN, Mullin K, et al. Alzheimer's disease risk gene CD33 inhibits microglial uptake of amyloid beta. *Neuron* 2013; 78: 631–643.

Guerreiro R, Wojtas A, Bras J, Carrasquillo M, Rogaeva E, Majounie E, et al. TREM2 variants in Alzheimer's disease. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 2013; 368: 117–127.

Guillot-Sestier M-V, Doty KR, Gate D, Rodriguez J, Leung BP, Rezai-Zadeh K, et al. Il10 deficiency rebalances innate immunity to mitigate Alzheimer-like pathology. *Neuron* 2015; 85: 534–548.

Guo Q. Investigation of the variability of the TSPO radioligand [11C]PBR28 in human brain. *BrainPET XXVIIth.* Vancouver, Canada: 2015.

Heneka MT, Carson MJ, El Khoury J, Landreth GE, Brosseron F, Feinstein DL, et al. Neuroinflammation in Alzheimer's disease. *Lancet Neurol.* 2015; 14: 388–405.

Herber DL, Mercer M, Roth LM, Symmonds K, Maloney J, Wilson N, et al. Microglial activation is required for Abeta clearance after intracranial injection of lipopolysaccharide in APP transgenic mice. *J. Neuroimmune Pharmacol. Off. J. Soc. NeuroImmune Pharmacol.*

2007; 2: 222–231.

Herber DL, Roth LM, Wilson D, Wilson N, Mason JE, Morgan D, et al. Time-dependent reduction in Abeta levels after intracranial LPS administration in APP transgenic mice. *Exp. Neurol.* 2004; 190: 245–253.

De Jong HWAM, van Velden FHP, Kloet RW, Buijs FL, Boellaard R, Lammertsma AA. Performance evaluation of the ECAT HRRT: an LSO-LYSO double layer high resolution, high sensitivity scanner. *Phys. Med. Biol.* 2007; 52: 1505–1526.

Koedam ELGE, Lauffer V, van der Vlies AE, van der Flier WM, Scheltens P, Pijnenburg YAL. Early-versus late-onset Alzheimer's disease: more than age alone. *J. Alzheimers Dis. JAD* 2010; 19: 1401–1408.

Kreisl WC, Lyoo CH, McGwier M, Snow J, Jenko KJ, Kimura N, et al. In vivo radioligand binding to translocator protein correlates with severity of Alzheimer's disease. *Brain J. Neurol.* 2013; 136: 2228–2238.

Lavisse S, García-Lorenzo D, Peyronneau M-A, Bodini B, Thiriez C, Kuhnast B, et al. Optimized Quantification of Translocator Protein Radioligand ¹⁸F-DPA-714 Uptake in the Brain of Genotyped Healthy Volunteers. *J. Nucl. Med. Off. Publ. Soc. Nucl. Med.* 2015; 56: 1048–1054.

Lockhart A, Davis B, Matthews JC, Rahmoune H, Hong G, Gee A, et al. The peripheral benzodiazepine receptor ligand PK11195 binds with high affinity to the acute phase reactant alpha1-acid glycoprotein: implications for the use of the ligand as a CNS inflammatory marker. *Nucl. Med. Biol.* 2003; 30: 199–206.

Lopresti BJ, Klunk WE, Mathis CA, Hoge JA, Ziolkowski SK, Lu X, et al. Simplified quantification of Pittsburgh Compound B amyloid imaging PET studies: a comparative analysis. *J. Nucl. Med. Off. Publ. Soc. Nucl. Med.* 2005; 46: 1959–1972.

Lyoo CH, Ikawa M, Liow J-S, Zoghbi SS, Morse CL, Pike VW, et al. Cerebellum Can Serve As a Pseudo-Reference Region in Alzheimer Disease to Detect Neuroinflammation Measured with PET Radioligand Binding to Translocator Protein. *J. Nucl. Med. Off. Publ. Soc. Nucl. Med.* 2015; 56: 701–706.

Michaud J-P, Rivest S. Anti-inflammatory signaling in microglia exacerbates Alzheimer's disease-related pathology. *Neuron* 2015; 85: 450–452.

Okello A, Koivunen J, Edison P, Archer HA, Turkheimer FE, Någren K, et al. Conversion of amyloid positive and negative MCI to AD over 3 years: an 11C-PIB PET study. *Neurology* 2009; 73: 754–760.

Owen DRJ, Gunn RN, Rabiner EA, Bennacef I, Fujita M, Kreisl WC, et al. Mixed-affinity binding in humans with 18-kDa translocator protein ligands. *J. Nucl. Med. Off. Publ. Soc. Nucl. Med.* 2011; 52: 24–32.

Prokop S, Miller KR, Heppner FL. Microglia actions in Alzheimer's disease. *Acta Neuropathol. (Berl.)* 2013; 126: 461–477.

Ramanan VK, Risacher SL, Nho K, Kim S, Shen L, McDonald BC, et al. GWAS of longitudinal amyloid accumulation on 18F-florbetapir PET in Alzheimer's disease implicates microglial activation gene IL1RAP. *Brain J. Neurol.* 2015; 138: 3076–3088.

Sarazin M, Berr C, De Rotrou J, Fabrigoule C, Pasquier F, Legrain S, et al. Amnestic syndrome of the medial temporal type identifies prodromal AD: a longitudinal study. *Neurology* 2007; 69: 1859–1867.

Schuitmaker A, Kropholler MA, Boellaard R, van der Flier WM, Kloet RW, van der Doef TF, et al. Microglial activation in Alzheimer's disease: an (R)-[¹¹C]PK11195 positron emission tomography study. *Neurobiol. Aging* 2013; 34: 128–136.

Shechter R, Schwartz M. Harnessing monocyte-derived macrophages to control central nervous system pathologies: no longer 'if' but 'how'. *J. Pathol.* 2013; 229: 332–346.

De Souza LC, Corlier F, Habert M-O, Uspenskaya O, Maroy R, Lamari F, et al. Similar amyloid- β burden in posterior cortical atrophy and Alzheimer's disease. *Brain J. Neurol.* 2011; 134: 2036–2043.

Sureau FC, Reader AJ, Comtat C, Leroy C, Ribeiro M-J, Buvat I, et al. Impact of image-space resolution modeling for studies with the high-resolution research tomograph. *J. Nucl. Med. Off. Publ. Soc. Nucl. Med.* 2008; 49: 1000–1008.

Varrone A, Oikonen V, Forsberg A, Joutsa J, Takano A, Solin O, et al. Positron emission tomography imaging of the 18-kDa translocator protein (TSPO) with [18F]FEMPA in Alzheimer's disease patients and control subjects. *Eur. J. Nucl. Med. Mol. Imaging* 2015; 42: 438–446.

Versijpt JJ, Dumont F, Van Laere KJ, Decoo D, Santens P, Audenaert K, et al. Assessment of neuroinflammation and microglial activation in Alzheimer's disease with radiolabelled PK11195 and single photon emission computed tomography. A pilot study. *Eur. Neurol.* 2003; 50: 39–47.

Van der Vlies AE, Koedam ELGE, Pijnenburg Y a. L, Twisk JWR, Scheltens P, van der Flier WM. Most rapid cognitive decline in APOE epsilon4 negative Alzheimer's disease with early onset. *Psychol. Med.* 2009; 39: 1907–1911.

Wiley CA, Lopresti BJ, Veneti S, Price J, Klunk WE, DeKosky ST, et al. Carbon 11-labeled Pittsburgh Compound B and carbon 11-labeled (R)-PK11195 positron emission tomographic imaging in Alzheimer disease. *Arch. Neurol.* 2009; 66: 60–67.

Wood P. *The Cerebellum in AD.* Totowa, New Jersey: 2003. p. 295–300.

Yasuno F, Kosaka J, Ota M, Higuchi M, Ito H, Fujimura Y, et al. Increased binding of peripheral benzodiazepine receptor in mild cognitive impairment-dementia converters measured by positron emission tomography with [¹¹C]DAA1106. *Psychiatry Res.* 2012; 203: 67–74.

Yasuno F, Ota M, Kosaka J, Ito H, Higuchi M, Doronbekov TK, et al. Increased binding of

peripheral benzodiazepine receptor in Alzheimer's disease measured by positron emission tomography with [¹¹C]DAA1106. *Biol. Psychiatry* 2008; 64: 835–841.

Tables

Table 1:

Title: Baseline characteristics.

	Controls (n=32)		AD patients (n= 64)	
	Controls defined by a negative PiB-PET (n=24)	Amyloidosis-controls defined by a positive PiB-PET (n=8)	Prodromal AD (n=38)	Dementia AD (n=26)
Age (years)	68.2 (8.4)	74.3 (9.8)	67.8 (9.1)	68.3 (12.1)
Sex (%male)	6 (25%)	4 (50%)	16 (42%)	8 (31%)
Carrier of ApoE ε4	0 (0%)	2 (25%)	24 (63%)*¶	13 (50%)*
MMSE score	29.5 (0.6)	29.1 (0.8)	24.1 (2.8)*¶	15.8 (4.5)*\$¶
CDR	CDR= 0 (n=24)	CDR=0 (n=8)	CDR=0.5 (n=38)* ¶	CDR>0.5 (n=26)*\$¶
HAB	11 (46%)	2 (25%)	17 (45%)	12 (46%)
MAB	9 (38%)	4 (50%)	17 (45%)	12 (46%)
LAB	4 (16%)	2 (25%)	4 (10%)	2 (8%)
IATI‡	N.A	N.A	0.46 (0.24)	0.36 (0.13)
[¹¹ C] PiB-GCI	1.24 (0.08)	2.19 (0.65)*	2.77 (0.56)*¶	2.87 (0.67)*¶

Legend:

Data are mean (SD) or number (%).

*p<0.05 compared to controls, defined by a negative PiB-PET (GCI<1.45) ;

¶p<0.05 compared to amyloidosis-controls, defined by a positive PiB-PET (GCI>1.45) ;

\$p<0.05 compared to prodromal AD.

‡Cerebrospinal fluid AD biomarker available for n=35 prodromal AD and n=21 dementia AD patients.

Table 2:

Title: [¹⁸F]DPA-714 standard uptake value-ratio in anatomical regions.

High Affinity Binders (HAB)	PiB-Controls (n=11)	AD patients (n=29)					
		All AD patients (n=29)	p value ^o	Prodromal AD (n=17)	p value*	AD Dementia (n=12)	p value*
Global Cortical Index	1.22 (0.07)	1.39 (0.20)	0.02	1.43 (0.22)	0.01	1.34 (0.16)	0.36
Frontal	1.22 (0.09)	1.36 (0.25)	0.23	1.41 (0.22)	0.09	1.29 (0.2)	1
Anterior Cingulate	1.28 (0.12)	1.37 (0.23)	0.55	1.42 (0.27)	0.36	1.30 (0.21)	1
Medium Cingulate	1.29 (0.09)	1.46 (0.23)	0.03	1.49 (0.26)	0.05	1.41 (0.19)	0.45
Posterior Cingulate	1.23 (0.11)	1.46 (0.21)	<0.001	1.48 (0.24)	0.004	1.43 (0.16)	0.04
Precuneus	1.15 (0.1)	1.37 (0.18)	<0.001	1.38 (0.21)	0.003	1.36 (0.15)	0.01
Parietal	1.19 (0.11)	1.40 (0.21)	0.003	1.42 (0.21)	0.01	1.37 (0.20)	0.1
Temporal	1.11 (0.06)	1.23 (0.12)	0.002	1.24 (0.13)	0.02	1.23 (0.12)	0.05
Hippocampus	1.28 (0.06)	1.31 (0.17)	0.74	1.34 (0.17)	0.89	1.26 (0.17)	1
Occipital	1.17 (0.07)	1.27 (0.14)	0.04	1.27 (0.15)	0.18	1.27 (0.14)	0.23
Mixed Affinity Binders (MAB)	PiB-Controls (n=9)	AD patients (n=29)					
		All AD patients (n=29)	p value ^o	Prodromal AD (n=17)	p value*	AD Dementia (n=12)	p value*
Global Cortical Index	1.20 (0.14)	1.38 (0.22)	0.02	1.42 (0.22)	0.04	1.33 (0.21)	0.4
Frontal	1.21 (0.18)	1.35 (0.25)	0.13	1.40 (0.25)	0.15	1.29 (0.25)	0.15
Anterior Cingulate	1.22 (0.19)	1.37 (0.27)	0.16	1.43 (0.26)	0.17	1.28 (0.27)	0.17
Medium Cingulate	1.26 (0.17)	1.45 (0.27)	0.04	1.49 (0.25)	0.101	1.39 (0.31)	0.10
Posterior Cingulate	1.27 (0.17)	1.49 (0.27)	0.05	1.49 (0.28)	0.14	1.48 (0.28)	0.14
Precuneus	1.15 (0.11)	1.41 (0.25)	0.003	1.42 (0.25)	0.01	1.39 (0.26)	0.02
Parietal	1.19 (0.15)	1.43 (0.26)	0.007	1.46 (0.29)	0.02	1.39 (0.22)	0.03
Temporal	1.09 (0.06)	1.23 (0.14)	0.004	1.23 (0.16)	0.03	1.22 (0.12)	0.04
Hippocampus	1.29 (0.10)	1.33 (0.28)	0.83	1.34 (0.32)	1	1.32 (0.24)	1
Occipital	1.17 (0.07)	1.31 (0.18)	0.01	1.33 (0.22)	0.09	1.29 (0.11)	0.09
HAB + MAB	PiB-Controls (n=20)	AD patients (n=58)					
		All AD patients (n=58)	p value ^o	Prodromal AD (n=34)	p value\$	AD Dementia (n=24)	p value\$
Global Cortical Index	1.21 (0.10)	1.42 (0.23)	<0.001	1.42 (0.22)	<0.001	1.34 (0.18)	0.09
Frontal	1.22 (0.13)	1.40 (0.25)	0.008	1.41 (0.26)	0.009	1.29 (0.23)	0.79
Anterior Cingulate	1.26 (0.15)	1.42 (0.26)	0.04	1.42 (0.26)	0.04	1.29 (0.24)	1
Medium Cingulate	1.27 (0.13)	1.49 (0.25)	0.002	1.49 (0.25)	0.004	1.40 (0.25)	0.20
Posterior Cingulate	1.25 (0.13)	1.49 (0.25)	<0.001	1.49 (0.26)	0.001	1.46 (0.22)	0.008
Precuneus	1.15 (0.10)	1.41 (0.22)	<0.001	1.40 (0.22)	<0.001	1.38 (0.21)	0.001
Parietal	1.19 (0.13)	1.44 (0.25)	<0.001	1.44 (0.25)	<0.001	1.38 (0.21)	0.02
Temporal	1.10 (0.06)	1.23 (0.15)	<0.001	1.24 (0.15)	0.001	1.23 (0.12)	0.004
Hippocampus	1.28 (0.08)	1.34 (0.25)	0.3	1.34 (0.25)	0.95	1.29 (0.21)	1
Occipital	1.17 (0.07)	1.30 (0.18)	0.006	1.30 (0.19)	0.01	1.28 (0.12)	0.05

Legend:

Data are mean (SD).

°p value compared to controls

*p value for ANOVA pairwise comparison to controls

\$p value for MANCOVA pairwise comparison to controls, adjusted to TSPO genotype.

Figure Legends:

Figure 1:

Title: Statistical parametric mapping analysis of [¹⁸F]DPA-714 binding (SUV_r) between (A) p-AD patients and controls and (B) between d-AD and controls, in the combined HAB+MAB group;

Legend: (1,3) "glass brain" representations and (2,4) sagittal, coronal and axial views (x=65, y=44 and z=37) with corresponding z-values.

Significance threshold set at p<0.05 family-wise error (FWE) corrected, with TSPO genotype as covariate.

Figure 2:

Title: Positive correlation between [¹⁸F]DPA-714 global cortical binding and MMSE and grey matter volume.

Legend: Positive correlation between $[^{18}\text{F}]\text{DPA-714}$ global cortical binding and: (a) MMSE, adjusted to age and TSPO genotype; (b) grey matter volume in AD patients, adjusted for age, TSPO genotype and CDR score in the HAB+MAB group; (c) grey matter volume in p-AD patients, adjusted for age and TSPO genotype.

Figure 3:

Title: Scatter and box plots showing global and regional $[^{18}\text{F}]\text{DPA-714}$ SUVr in anatomical regions across groups.

Legend: (-)=Controls, defined by a negative PiB-PET (in yellow); (+)=Amyloidosis controls, defined by a positive PiB-PET (in green) in the HAB+MAB population.

* $p < 0.05$ adjusted for age, TSPO genotype and initial MMSE score.

Figure 4:

Title: Correlations between $[^{11}\text{C}]\text{PiB}$ and $[^{18}\text{F}]\text{DPA-714}$.

Legend: (a) Global cortical index SUVr and (b) precuneus SUVr in the AD patient group, in the HAB+MAB population [p-AD (red triangles) and d-AD (blue diamonds)].

r =correlation coefficient with TSPO genotype, age, CDR score and ApoE4 status as covariates.

Figure 5:

Title: Scatter and box plots showing global and regional [¹⁸F]DPA-714 SUVr in anatomical regions across Fast Decliners and Slow Decliners AD patients in the HAB+MAB population.

Legend: FD: Fast decliners, in red (increasing CDR score of 0.5 or more after a two years follow-up); SD: Slow Decliners, in blue (CDR score remaining stable after a two years follow-up).

** $p < 0.005$, * $p < 0.05$ with age, TSPO genotype and initial MMSE score as covariates.